

Common mistakes in learning language

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Annotation: This article discusses common mistakes in language learning and their analysis.

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Learning a new language is like a new challenge to your brain. You feel excited, anxious, overwhelmed, and proud of yourself during the process. Never forget that going outside of your comfort zone is the key to learning. Still, you can make it easier if you try to avoid some common mistakes of learning English or another language you want to learn!

People are different but some learning methods, like immersion, work perfectly for every person. That is why we can make a list of the common mistakes language learners make and offer you the solution against them. You can feel surprised to see how many of these mistakes you have done constantly! Information is power, so even knowing these are a mistake, will change a lot of your learning journey.

When we decide to learn a new language, our brains feel uncomfortable, and try to find some similarities between our mother tongue and the new language. We need to stop doing this, even if it is hard at the beginning. Most of us are used to think a sentence in our primitive language, then try to make a sentence according to that planned one. It doesn't help your learning process at all because you set boundaries to your brain about what it should think and say. However, there is countless way to say something with different words. You may think of a very complex sentence in your primitive language but if you don't limit yourself with saying/writing the exact sentence, you can give the main idea with lots of alternatives. You may divide the idea into two or three sentences and still, you can give the message you want to transfer.

Here is the most common mistake in learning a new language process! Sadly, speaking and writing are the best to improve your language level, yet most of us are too scared of doing these. In my learning experience, I was always too anxious to talk or write in English for years. I had felt insufficient, and sometimes still feeling it. But it is not a good excuse to stop trying. You will improve your English or another new language level by doing it. Even if it means doing mistakes from time to time. Never

let your mistakes stop you. Try to learn from them, and keep doing your best. They don't have egos like us. They don't think that they will be humiliated if they choose the wrong word or make a very weird sentence. If they would think those sentences will make them embarrassed, they may choose to not talk. It would be a great loss, don't you think? All of us are these babies who had learned our primitive languages and we speak them great for years. Because we didn't be afraid of trying to talk, listen, write or read. They are wonderful role models for our learning a new language journey! Translate services are great artificial intelligence products, but it can be dangerous to use them too much. Yes, they are fast and at some points very helpful but if you are decisive to learn a new language, you should use them carefully. Writing your sentences or reading a piece of writing and understand it on your own are important. If you use them a lot, it can become a habit. Then, you can feel so annoyed when you need to write or read in that language without using these services. This is a childhood memory and almost all of us have very similar stories most probably. But when you become an adult, you need to understand that you have to stop doing it. Learning a new language requires some courage, and it is not easy for anyone. Making each other embarrassed with wrong pronunciations or feeling bad because of your imperfect accent is not right. For sure we need to have a good accent to understand each other. This is the main step of communication, but like everything else, this will happen in time. If you feel embarrassed because of your accent, you can stop trying it. This is the real waste, not your accent or your mistakes.

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